

OECD EKONOMİLERİNDE KÜRESEL TEDARİK ZİNCİRİ BASKILARININ DALGACIK ANALİZİ: PETROL FİYATLARI, ENDÜSTRİYEL ÜRETİM VE DÖVİZ KURLARININ ASİMETRİK ROLLERİ

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Öz: Bu çalışma, OECD ekonomilerinde küresel tedarik zinciri baskılarının belirleyicilerini incelemekte ve özellikle petrol fiyatları, endüstriyel üretim ve döviz kurlarının asimetrik etkilerine odaklanmaktadır. 1998-2025 dönemine ait aylık veriler ve Küresel Tedarik Zinciri Baskı Endeksi (GSCPI) kullanılarak, zaman-frekans dinamiklerini yakalamak amacıyla dalgacık güç spektrumu (WPS) ve dalgacık eşgüdüm analizi (WTC) yöntemleri uygulanmıştır. Bulgular, petrol fiyatlarının tedarik zinciri stresi üzerinde en güçlü belirleyici olduğunu ve özellikle 2008 küresel finansal krizi, 2014 petrol fiyatı çöküşü ve COVID-19 pandemisi gibi büyük krizlerde bu etkinin belirginleştiğini göstermektedir. Endüstriyel üretim (toplam talep) şokları asimetrik etkilere sahiptir; pozitif şoklar baskıları artırırken, negatif şokların hafifletici etkisi daha sınırlı kalmaktadır. Döviz kuru dalgalanmaları ise ithalat maliyet kanalı üzerinden baskıyı artırmakta, hem geçişkenlik hem de geri besleme etkileri sergilemektedir. Bu bulgular, tedarik zinciri baskılarının çok boyutlu yapısını ortaya koymakta ve dayanıklılığın artırılabilmesi için zaman-frekans duyarlı politika çerçevelerinin gerekliliğini vurgulamaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Küresel Tedarik Zinciri Baskıları, Asimetrik Etkiler, Dalgacık Analizi, Zaman-Frekans Dinamikleri, OECD Ekonomileri

JEL Kodları: C32, E31, F44

WAVELET ANALYSIS OF GLOBAL SUPPLY CHAIN PRESSURES IN OECD ECONOMIES: THE ASYMMETRIC ROLE OF OIL PRICES, INDUSTRIAL PRODUCTION, AND EXCHANGE RATES

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Abstract: This paper examines the factors contributing to global supply chain pressures in OECD countries, focusing on the asymmetric impact of oil prices, industrial production and exchange rates. With a structured dataset spanning the month from 1998 to 2025 and the Global Supply Chain Pressure Index (GSCPI), the wavelet power spectrum (WPS) and wavelet transform coherence (WTC) methods are used to capture time-frequency dynamics. Findings reveal that oil price is the asset with the highest spillover impact on the supply chain stress, particularly during systemic crises, including the 2008 global financial crisis, the 2014 oil price crash, and most recently, the COVID-19 pandemic. There is asymmetry in the effects of industrial production (aggregate demand) shocks such that the contributions of positive aggregate demand shocks to increasing pressures are greater than the contributions of the negative ones to reducing them. Variation of exchange rates adds stress through import cost channels and has both pass-through and feedback effects. These results emphasize the multifaceted nature of the supply chain pressures and underscore the importance of policy frameworks that include time-frequency monitoring to augment system resilience.

Keywords: Global Supply Chain Pressures, Asymmetric Effects, Wavelet Analysis, OECD Economies

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INTRODUCTION

The increasing interconnectedness of global production networks has heightened the vulnerability of economies to disruptions in the flow of goods, services, and intermediate inputs. In recent years, the magnitude of such disruptions has been unprecedented, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic and the subsequent recovery phase. The Global Supply Chain Pressure Index (GSCPI), developed by the Federal Reserve Bank of New York, has emerged as a comprehensive and widely adopted metric to quantify these disruptions. By combining data on freight rates, supplier delivery times, and international trade volumes, the GSCPI offers a unified measure that reflects both supply- and demand-driven pressures (Benigno, di Giovanni, Fornaro, & Noble, 2022; New York Fed, 2022). Its integration into empirical macroeconomic research has enabled a more precise understanding of how global bottlenecks translate into domestic price dynamics (New York Fed, n.d.).

The macroeconomic consequences of supply chain disruptions have been examined extensively in recent literature, particularly in relation to inflation. Ascari, Bonam, and Smadu (2024), using a Bayesian SVAR framework for the euro area, find that shocks to the GSCPI were a dominant driver of the 2022 surge in core inflation, generating hump-shaped and persistent effects that challenge conventional Phillips curve models. Similarly, Gordon and Clark (2023) highlight that in the United States, both aggregate demand and supply factors—including supply chain disturbances—played significant roles in the inflationary spike of 2021–2022. These findings reinforce the notion that supply chain stress is not merely a transitory logistical challenge but a macroeconomic force with enduring impacts.

From an identification perspective, distinguishing supply chain shocks from other macroeconomic shocks, such as energy supply disruptions, is critical. De Santis (2024) addresses this by jointly identifying supply chain and energy supply shocks within a structural BVAR for the euro area. His results indicate that adverse supply chain shocks exert more persistent upward pressure on core HICP and inflation expectations than energy supply shocks, which tend to have more transient effects. This distinction is particularly relevant for OECD economies, where energy import dependence varies widely.

Among the determinants of supply chain pressures, oil prices stand out as a key factor due to their role in transportation, production, and global trade costs. Williams (2025), using local projection methods, finds that oil price increases—especially during periods of elevated geopolitical risk—exert disproportionately strong upward effects on the GSCPI. Kilian (2009) seminal work on oil market shocks further reveals that the macroeconomic impact of oil price changes depends on whether they are driven by supply or demand factors, implying heterogeneous spillovers to logistics costs and capacity constraints.

Global demand conditions also play a substantial role. Ha (2023) demonstrates that positive global demand shocks, proxied by industrial production, exacerbate supply chain pressures more than negative shocks alleviate them, suggesting asymmetric adjustment processes. Freeman and Baldwin (2020) similarly emphasize that synchronized recoveries, such as the post-pandemic rebound, intensify bottlenecks through heightened competition for scarce logistical resources.

Exchange rates represent another important channel through which macroeconomic conditions affect supply chain pressures. Currency depreciations increase the local currency cost of imported intermediate inputs, potentially amplifying stress in production networks. Campa and Goldberg (2005) show that exchange rate pass-through into import prices is partial but significant

in OECD economies, with variation across industries and time horizons. Complementary evidence by Chen, Rogoff, and Rossi (2010) highlights the predictive power of commodity-linked exchange rates for global commodity prices, underscoring the bidirectional relationship between exchange rates and tradable goods markets.

In addition to oil prices and exchange rates, transportation costs exert independent influence on supply chain conditions. Carrière-Swallow et al. (2022) find that shipping cost spikes, as measured by the Baltic Dry Index, lead to substantial and persistent increases in import prices and inflation across countries, effects that are in some cases more enduring than those of oil or food price shocks.

Against this backdrop, the present study examines the determinants of global supply chain pressures in OECD economies, focusing on the asymmetric roles of oil prices, aggregate demand, and exchange rates. Using the GSCPI as the dependent variable, the analysis incorporates secondary monthly data on OECD aggregate industrial production, nominal effective exchange rates, and global oil prices from January 1998 to June 2025. The study adopts an econometric framework that allows for asymmetric effects, recognizing that positive and negative shocks may influence supply chain pressures differently. By centering the analysis on OECD aggregate data, this research contributes to the literature by providing a unified cross-country perspective, bridging the gap between case-specific studies and broader global analyses.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND BRIEF LITERATURE REVIEW

The theoretical foundation of this study lies at the intersection of international macroeconomics, trade theory, and the economics of global production networks. The central focus is on understanding the determinants of global supply chain pressures (GSCPI) within the context of OECD economies and assessing how oil prices, aggregate demand (proxied by industrial production), and nominal effective exchange rates jointly shape these pressures.

Global supply chains are complex, multi-tiered networks through which intermediate goods and final products flow across borders before reaching end consumers. The efficiency and resilience of these networks depend on factors such as transportation costs, production capacity, and the smooth functioning of logistics systems (Freeman & Baldwin, 2020). Disruptions at any point—whether driven by supply-side shocks, demand surges, or macroeconomic volatility—can create bottlenecks that propagate internationally. The GSCPI, developed by Benigno, et al. (2022), encapsulates this dynamic by aggregating multiple indicators of trade, shipping, and delivery delays into a single monthly measure.

Oil Prices and Supply Chain Pressures

Oil prices are a primary determinant of transportation and production costs, affecting supply chains through both direct and indirect channels. In the direct channel, higher crude oil prices increase fuel costs for maritime shipping, trucking, and air freight, thereby raising the cost of moving goods between production and consumption points (Kilian, 2009). In the indirect channel, oil price increases raise input costs for energy-intensive industries, such as chemicals, metals, and plastics, which are critical intermediate goods in global value chains. Williams (2025) shows that oil price spikes, particularly when accompanied by elevated geopolitical risk, significantly increase GSCPI values, indicating an immediate amplification of supply chain pressures.

From a theoretical perspective, oil prices can be decomposed into supply-driven and demand-driven components (Kilian, 2009). Supply-driven oil price shocks—caused by production disruptions in oil-exporting countries—reduce available shipping and production capacity, amplifying bottlenecks. Demand-driven oil price shocks—associated with global economic expansions—raise freight costs as part of broader demand pressures. In the OECD context, where manufacturing and trade integration are high, both types of shocks can generate nonlinear effects on supply chain pressures, with demand-driven shocks potentially compounding existing bottlenecks.

Aggregate Demand and Industrial Production

Aggregate demand conditions are closely tied to supply chain stress through the capacity utilization channel. Industrial production, especially at the aggregate OECD level, serves as a proxy for global demand for intermediate and final goods. Positive demand shocks—such as synchronized recoveries from recessions—can outstrip existing production and transportation capacity, leading to congestion in shipping routes, extended delivery times, and increased input prices (Ha, 2023). Freeman and Baldwin (2020) argue that such synchronized expansions are particularly problematic in highly integrated supply chains, where spare capacity is limited, and expansion requires significant time and capital investment.

The theoretical relationship between demand and supply chain pressures can be characterized by asymmetry. When demand rises sharply, supply chain pressures intensify quickly due to fixed short-term capacity constraints in manufacturing plants, ports, and transportation fleets. Conversely, when demand falls, pressures do not necessarily dissipate at the same pace because of contractual rigidities, labor market frictions, and the time needed to reallocate resources (Ha, 2023). This asymmetric adjustment implies that empirical models should test for nonlinearities in the response of GSCPI to demand fluctuations.

Exchange Rates and Import Costs

Nominal effective exchange rates (NEERs) affect supply chain pressures primarily through their impact on the local-currency cost of imported goods and intermediate inputs. In OECD economies, where production often relies on a significant share of imported components, currency depreciation raises the domestic price of these inputs, potentially intensifying cost-push pressures (Campa & Goldberg, 2005). Exchange rate movements also influence the competitiveness of exports, which can alter production and shipping volumes in ways that either exacerbate or alleviate bottlenecks.

The degree of exchange rate pass-through (ERPT) into import prices is crucial in determining the strength of this relationship. Campa and Goldberg (2005) find that ERPT is partial but significant across OECD economies, with higher pass-through in sectors characterized by low product differentiation and limited pricing-to-market behavior. Chen, Rogoff, and Rossi (2010) add that exchange rates linked to commodity markets can also signal changes in global production costs, further connecting currency movements to supply chain dynamics. From a theoretical standpoint, exchange rate depreciation can have dual effects: while it raises import costs (increasing GSCPI), it may also reduce foreign demand for exports if capacity constraints are binding, thereby relieving some pressure.

Integrating the Variables into a Unified Framework

In the context of OECD economies, oil prices, aggregate demand, and exchange rates operate simultaneously, often reinforcing each other's effects on supply chain pressures. For example, a global demand boom can raise oil prices, which in turn increases transportation and input costs, while exchange rate depreciation magnifies the domestic impact of these higher prices. Conversely, a global slowdown may lower oil prices and reduce demand, but adverse currency movements could still maintain elevated cost pressures.

Graph 1. Theoretical Framework: Determinants of GSCPI in OECD Economies

(Source: Created by the author.)

This study adopts a framework where the GSCPI serves as the dependent variable, capturing the net effect of all such interactions. The independent variables—global oil prices, OECD industrial production index, and OECD aggregate nominal effective exchange rate—are chosen to represent the most theoretically and empirically supported channels of influence. Given the possibility of asymmetric effects, the empirical strategy will allow for differential impacts of positive and negative shocks to these variables. This approach aligns with the insights from Ha (2023) on demand asymmetry, Kilian (2009) on oil price decomposition, and Campa and Goldberg (2005) on exchange rate pass-through.

By grounding the analysis in established macroeconomic theory while focusing on the unique vulnerabilities of integrated OECD supply chains, this framework aims to contribute both to academic literature and to policy discussions on how to mitigate the systemic risks posed by global supply chain disruptions.

DATA AND METHODOLOGY

This study utilizes a monthly panel dataset covering the period from January 1998 to June 2025 to investigate the determinants of global supply chain pressures in the context of OECD economies. The dependent variable is the Global Supply Chain Pressure Index (GSCPI), developed by Benigno, et al. (2022) and published by the Federal Reserve Bank of New York. The GSCPI aggregates multiple indicators—such as shipping costs, delivery times, and trade volume imbalances—into a standardized measure of supply chain stress. Higher values indicate greater disruption and tighter supply chain conditions.

The main independent variables are selected to capture key macroeconomic drivers of supply chain pressures:

1. Oil Prices: Measured as the monthly average Brent crude oil price in U.S. dollars per barrel, obtained from the U.S. Energy Information Administration (EIA). Oil prices are included due to their direct influence on transportation and production costs, and their indirect effects on input prices for energy-intensive industries (Kilian, 2009).

2. OECD Industrial Production Index (IPI): Sourced from the OECD Main Economic Indicators database, this index serves as a proxy for aggregate demand and capacity utilization within OECD economies. Industrial production is widely used in empirical research to capture cyclical demand conditions that influence the volume and speed of goods movement (Freeman & Baldwin, 2020).

3. OECD Effective Exchange Rate (EER): Derived from the Bank for International Settlements (BIS) and OECD statistics, this measure reflects trade-weighted exchange rate movements for the OECD area. Exchange rates influence the domestic currency cost of imported goods and inputs, thereby affecting production costs and export competitiveness (Campa & Goldberg, 2005).

The variables employed in this study were carefully selected to capture the key determinants of supply chain pressures in OECD economies. The selection process prioritized macroeconomic indicators widely recognized in the literature, along with data sources of high reliability. Accordingly, the analysis incorporates the GSCPI, oil prices, the industrial production index, and the effective exchange rate. The definitions, measurement methods, frequencies, and actual data sources for each variable are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Data Sources and Definitions

Variable	Definition	Frequency	Period	Source
GSCPI	Global Supply Chain Pressure Index – Composite indicator combining shipping costs, delivery times, and trade volumes	Monthly	1998M1 – 2025M6	Federal Reserve Bank of New York – Liberty Street Economics (Benigno et al., 2022)
Oil Prices	Brent crude oil price, USD per barrel	Monthly	1998M1 – 2025M6	U.S. Energy Information Administration (EIA)
Industrial Production Index (OECD)	Index of total industrial production for OECD economies, 2015=100	Monthly	1998M1 – 2025M6	OECD Main Economic Indicators (MEI)
Effective Exchange Rate (OECD)	Trade-weighted exchange rate index for OECD economies (BIS narrow index)	Monthly	1998M1 – 2025M6	Bank for International Settlements (BIS), OECD Statistics

Following the definition of the variables, a comprehensive dataset covering the analysis period was compiled and subjected to preliminary statistical examination. Understanding the central tendencies, ranges, and variability of the variables is essential, as these characteristics directly influence the predictive capacity and robustness of the econometric models. In this context, Table 2 reports the descriptive statistics for all variables used in the study, including their mean values, standard deviations, minimum and maximum observations, as well as interquartile ranges.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics (January 1998 – June 2025)

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	25th %	Median	75th %	Max
GSCPI	0.0070	1.0051	-1.5692	-0.5978	-0.2641	0.1713	4.4517
Crude Oil Price (Brent, USD/barrel)	63.1039	30.5298	9.8000	37.7700	63.1400	82.9050	133.8700
Industrial Production Index (OECD, 2015=100)	97.4260	9.0183	78.8390	89.9055	96.9184	106.2415	111.9266
Effective Exchange Rate (OECD)	1.1827	0.1544	0.8525	1.0820	1.1698	1.3009	1.5

Note: All variables are in monthly frequency. CPI and Industrial Production are OECD aggregate indices (2015=100). Oil prices are monthly averages of Brent crude oil in U.S. dollars per barrel. Effective Exchange Rate is the OECD aggregate index (base=1). All series are expressed in levels prior to transformation.

Table 2 provides descriptive statistics for the variables used in the analysis. The GSCPI fluctuates between -1.57 and 4.45, indicating that both extreme supply chain easing and tightening episodes occurred during the sample period. Oil prices exhibit high volatility, with a minimum of 9.8 USD/barrel during the late 1990s and early 2000s crises, and a peak of 133.87 USD/barrel during the 2008 oil price shock. Industrial production in OECD economies demonstrates cyclical variations around its mean of 97.43, consistent with global economic expansions and contractions. The effective exchange rate index varies between 0.85 and 1.57, suggesting considerable exchange rate fluctuations over the sample period, potentially impacting import costs and competitiveness.

To ensure the validity of the subsequent econometric analysis, it is essential to examine the stationarity properties of the variables included in the model. Non-stationary time series can lead to spurious regression results, undermining the reliability of statistical inferences. Therefore, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) unit root tests were employed to formally assess the presence of unit roots in each series. Both tests are widely used in empirical macroeconomic research, with the ADF test accounting for higher-order serial correlation through lagged difference terms, and the PP test providing non-parametric corrections for serial correlation and heteroskedasticity. The results, reported in Table 3, allow us to determine the integration order of each variable and guide the appropriate econometric specification for the subsequent analysis.

Table 3. ADF and PP Unit Root Test Results

Variables	ADF		PP	
	Intercept	Trend and Intercept	Intercept	Trend and Intercept
GSCPI	-3.541 (0.007)	-3.822 (0.016)	-3.493 (0.008)	-3.834 (0.015)
OIL	-2.658 (0.082)	-2.864 (0.175)	-2.249 (0.189)	-2.425 (0.365)

IP	-1.836 (0.362)	-3.595 (0.031)	-1.807 (0.376)	-3.804 (0.017)
EER	-1.575 (0.494)	-2.596 (0.282)	-1.355 (0.604)	-2.368 (0.395)
Δ GSCPI	-16.627 (0.000)	-16.602 (0.000)	-17.510 (0.000)	-17.476 (0.000)
Δ OIL	-12.776 (0.000)	-12.768 (0.000)	-12.597 (0.000)	-12.584 (0.000)
Δ IP	-14.898 (0.000)	-14.880 (0.000)	-15.140 (0.000)	-15.119 (0.000)
Δ EER	-14.035 (0.000)	-14.014 (0.000)	-13.950 (0.000)	-13.929 (0.000)

(Note: The values in parentheses in the Table 3 are the p value.)

The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) tests were employed to determine the order of integration of the variables, considering both intercept and trend specifications. The results indicate that the Global Supply Chain Pressure Index (GSCPI) is stationary at level $I(0)$ under both ADF and PP tests, with statistically significant test statistics ($p < 0.05$). This suggests that supply chain pressures exhibit mean-reverting behavior and do not contain a unit root over the sample period.

In contrast, Oil prices (OIL), Industrial Production Index (IP), and Effective Exchange Rate (EER) are non-stationary at level, as indicated by high p-values in both ADF and PP tests under all deterministic specifications. However, the first differences of these variables are stationary ($p < 0.01$), confirming that they are integrated of order one, $I(1)$.

These findings reveal a mixed order of integration among the variables:

$I(0)$: GSCPI $I(1)$: OIL, IP, EER

Although unit root tests are used for control purposes, series can be $I(0)$ or $I(1)$; there is no stationarity requirement in the Wavelet Power Spectrum and Wavelet Transform Coherence analyses (Nieves-González et al., 2022; Torrence & Compo, 1998).

METHODOLOGY

The Wavelet Power Spectrum (WPS) offers a method of investigating the localized variance of a single time series in both the time and frequency planes. In contrast to conventional Fourier-based approaches that assume stationarity and provide a global perspective on frequencies, WPS is tailored for non-stationary macroeconomic series because it extracts both transient and persistent dynamics simultaneously. The method is based on the Continuous Wavelet Transform (CWT), which decomposes a time series into scale contributions, and then squares the wavelet coefficients to derive the local power spectrum. This conversion enabled researchers to ascertain when and at what frequencies there was relatively more volatility or more of a cyclical component, especially when there were more or fewer disturbances in economic activity. The Morlet wavelet

is widely used because of its best compromise between time and frequency localization (Torrence & Compo, 1998). In terms of WPS plots, the x-axis is time, the y-axis is frequency (or scale), and the color represents the strength of the variance within each time–frequency location. Statistical significance is commonly measured concerning a red-noise ambient, and the cone-of-influence (COI) to identify regions with potential edge effects. By identifying the inherent oscillatory nature of each series, WPS provides a crucial first step that facilitates the interpretation of a single series and an analytical framework to assess time–frequency co-movements through WTC (Wavelet Transform Coherence).

This study employs Wavelet Transform Coherence (WTC) to analyze the time–frequency co-movement between global supply chain pressures (GSCPI) and three key macroeconomic variables for OECD economies: international oil prices (OIL), industrial production (IP), and the nominal effective exchange rate (EER). WTC is particularly well-suited for this context, as these variables exhibit strong non-stationarity, structural breaks, and potentially time-varying correlations—especially during global shocks such as the 2008 financial crisis and the 2020 COVID-19 pandemic.

Following Torrence and Compo (1998) and Grinsted et al. (2004), the continuous wavelet transform (CWT) of a time series $x(t)$ is defined as:

$$W_{GSCPI}(s, \tau) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{s}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} GSCPI(t) \psi_0^* \left(\frac{t - \tau}{s} \right) dt$$

where s is the scale (inversely related to frequency), τ is the time localization, and ψ_0^* denotes the complex conjugate of the Morlet mother wavelet—selected for its superior balance between time and frequency resolution in macroeconomic applications (Aguar-Conraria & Soares, 2014).

Similarly, the wavelet transform for each explanatory variable is given by:

$$W_{OIL}(s, \tau), W_{IP}(s, \tau), W_{EER}(s, \tau)$$

The cross wavelet transform (XWT) between GSCPI and each explanatory variable $y(t)$ (OIL, IP, or EER) is expressed as:

$$W_{GSCPI,y}(s, \tau) = W_{GSCPI}(s, \tau) \cdot W_y^*(s, \tau)$$

The wavelet coherence between GSCPI and $y(t)$ is then defined as:

$$R_{GSCPI,y}^2(s, \tau) = \frac{|S(s^{-1}W_{GSCPI,y}(s, \tau))|^2}{S(s^{-1}|W_{GSCPI}(s, \tau)|^2) \cdot S(s^{-1}|W_y(s, \tau)|^2)}$$

where $S(\cdot)$ is a smoothing operator applied in both time and scale dimensions. The squared coherence coefficient R^2 ranges between 0 (no local correlation) and 1 (perfect local correlation).

The phase difference between GSCPI and $y(t)$ is given by:

$$\phi_{GSCPI,y}(s, \tau) = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\delta \{S(s^{-1}W_{GSCPI,y}(s, \tau))\}}{\Re \{S(s^{-1}W_{GSCPI,y}(s, \tau))\}} \right)$$

In the WTC plots, phase arrows convey both the sign of the relationship and the lead–lag structure, where rightward arrows indicate positive correlation (in-phase), leftward arrows indicate negative correlation (anti-phase), upward arrows signify that the explanatory variable

leads GSCPI by 90°, and downward arrows indicate that GSCPI leads the explanatory variable by 90°. WTC is superior to standard time-series methods such as VAR and ARDL when the aim is to uncover time-varying, frequency-dependent interactions. In this study, the relationship between GSCPI and oil prices (OIL) is expected to capture cost-push channels, particularly during energy price shocks (Baumeister & Kilian, 2016), while the link between GSCPI and industrial production (IP) allows for the detection of demand-driven supply chain stress during recessions and recoveries (Carvalho et al., 2021), and the GSCPI–EER interaction explores exchange rate pass-through into import costs and subsequent supply chain constraints (Amiti et al., 2014). The multi-resolution nature of WTC enables the identification of short-run (0.5–1 year) and medium-run (1–4 years) linkages, thereby distinguishing between temporary disruptions and persistent structural relationships. In the context of OECD supply chain analysis, WTC offers distinct advantages, such as capturing crisis effects by identifying whether linkages strengthen during events like the 2008 global financial crisis, the 2014 oil price collapse, or the COVID-19 pandemic, providing frequency-specific insights by determining whether short-term volatility or long-term trends dominate the interaction, and offering lead–lag clarity through phase analysis to distinguish whether macroeconomic shocks precede or follow supply chain pressures.

EMPIRICAL FINDINGS

Wavelet Power Spectrum (WPS) Analysis

Before examining the time–frequency co-movement patterns between variables, it is essential to investigate the dominant periodicities and volatility dynamics within each series individually. The Wavelet Power Spectrum (WPS) offers a two-dimensional decomposition of variance over time and across frequencies, allowing for the detection of both persistent and transient cycles (Torrence & Compo, 1998). Graphs for the GSCPI, oil prices (OIL), industrial production (IP), and the nominal effective exchange rate (EER) are presented below, with the color scale indicating the magnitude of variance (blue = low, red = high) and the thick black contours denoting regions significant at the 5% level.

GSCPI: The Wavelet Power Spectrum (WPS) for the GSCPI is given by Graph 2. The color legend shows the extent of variation, with red indicating high power and blue indicating low power. The thick black contours delineate the statistically significant regions at 5%, and the cone of influence (COI) indicates the range over which edge effects could affect the outcome. Spectrum exhibits sharp fluctuation clumps on the medium-term cycles of cycle (~1-2 years) around 2007–2010, when the global financial crisis led to turmoil in international trade and supply chains. There is evidence of a fresh surge of power after 2015–16, again centered around the 1–2 year maturity band, reflecting cyclical forces possibly related to trade tensions, geopolitical uncertainty, and variations in global demand. The most significant concentration of variance is found during 2020–2022, where we find above random clustering for both short-term (~3–6 months) and intermediate-term cycles (~1–2 years). These trends align with the sharp and broad-based disruptions created by the pandemic. Conclusion: The WPS demonstrates that the GSCPI is episodic in terms of its short-run volatility, and that both short-run and medium-run cycles are present, with the major episodes coinciding with world recession.

Graph 2. Wavelet Power Spectrum - GSCPI

(Note: Color intensity indicates the magnitude of variance in the series. Thick black contours indicate regions with a 5% significance level, indicating cone (COI) edge effects.)

Oil Prices (OIL): Global oil prices WPS are shown in Graph 3. The colour scale indicates the size of the variation (red = large, blue = small), and the thick black contours show where the variation is statistically significant at the 5% level. The circle of influence (COI) identifies the radius beyond which edge effects may be present. The spectrum exhibits large power in short-to medium-term bands (~ 0.5 – 2 years), especially during the 2007–2010 period, corresponding to the rapid rise and subsequent fall of oil prices during the global financial crisis. It can also be seen that a second very important cluster around 2014–2016, which is also the time of the big oil price fall, is concentrated again in the 1–2 year cycle. Furthermore, the 2020–2021 period also presents some new variability attributed to the COVID-19 pandemic, in which both the demand and supply shocks affected the energy markets. Even shorter-run variations (≈ 3 – 6 months) become apparent but tend to be less persistent, perhaps reflecting temporary market shocks and inventory changes. In general terms, the WPS emphasises that oil price volatility is largely dominated by medium-term cyclical patterns (1–2 years) interspersed with abrupt episodic shocks during the main global crisis. The results highlight the structural function of the oil markets in relaying the cost-push effect to the overall economy.

Graph 3. Wavelet Power Spectrum - OIL

(Note: Color intensity indicates the magnitude of variance in the series. Thick black contours indicate regions with a 5% significance level, indicating cone (COI) edge effects.)

Industrial Production (IP): Graph 4 shows the WPS for global industrial production. Color image represents the magnitude of the variance (red=high, blue=low) while heavy black contours indicate statistically significant areas at the 5% level. The cone of influence (COI) indicates where edge effects can negatively impact interpretation. The spectrum shows considerable modulation of the medium-term cycle (~ 1–2 years) during 2008–2010, which is due to the abrupt bursting of the bubble in the global manufacturing sector following the announcement of the global financial crisis. A second such long-lasting and strong cluster occurred during 2020–2021, due to the COVID-19 outbreak, which shut down factories and the associated diffusion-disruption cascade. Besides these medium-term oscillations, the WPS identifies shorter-cycle fluctuations in the band at 0.5 years (6 months) related to crisis episodes, which would reflect sudden swings in industrial activity due to demand breakdowns and production stoppages. In general, the WPS also suggests international downturns greatly impact industrial production, and the 1–2 year cyclical component contributes most to variance in periods of large crises. The existence of medium-term cycles and temporary high-frequency spikes highlights the duality of industrial production shocks: persistent patterns of cyclic contractions and temporary high-frequency disturbances.

Graph 4. Wavelet Power Spectrum - IP

(Note: Color intensity indicates the magnitude of variance in the series. Thick black contours indicate regions with a 5% significance level, indicating cone (COI) edge effects.)

Effective Exchange Rate (EER): The wavelet power spectrum (WPS) of the nominal EER is presented in Graph 5. The color code is the amplitude of the variation (red is high, blue is low). At the same time, the bold black contours are the statistically significant regions at the 5% level. The COI is the interval wherein results are dependable, while edge distortions can affect beyond. The spectrum depicts considerable variability at the short-term band ($\approx 0.25-0.5$ years) in the early 2000s, indicating peaks of increased exchange rate volatility in response to financial instability and currency market corrections. A significant variance cluster also arises at the mid-term scale ($\approx 1-2$ years) during 2008-2012, corresponding to the global financial crisis and policy-induced shifts towards equilibrium in currency markets. In 2015, additional large fluctuations emerged in the 1-year cycle, hinting that volatility episodes no longer come and go abruptly and could be indicative of ongoing turbulence driven by changes in monetary policy, global capital flow, and pressures from trade. Short-run clusters revived in the late 2010s and early 2020s, but are quantitatively less robust than during previous crises. The WPS shows that the EER is dominated by short-frequency variance and occasional spikes in middle-term cycles. These findings point to the sensitivity of exchange rates to both temporary disturbances and cyclical changes in international financial markets.

Graph 5. Wavelet Power Spectrum - EER

(Note: Color intensity indicates the magnitude of variance in the series. Thick black contours indicate regions with a 5% significance level, indicating cone (COI) edge effects.)

The wavelet power spectrum (WPS) results for the global supply chain pressures, oil prices, industrial production, and the effective exchange rate reveal distinct time–frequency patterns that align with major global disruptions. The GSCPI shows strong variance in the 1–2 year band during 2007–2010 and 2020–2022, reflecting the global financial crisis and the COVID-19 pandemic, while short-term fluctuations (3–6 months) also emerge during the latter. Oil prices are dominated by medium-term cycles, with significant clusters in 2007–2010, the 2014–2016 collapse, and renewed volatility in 2020–2021. Industrial production exhibits pronounced variance in the 1–2 year cycle during 2008–2010 and 2020–2021, underscoring its cyclical sensitivity to recessions, along with short-lived spikes around six months. The effective exchange rate is marked by short-term volatility in the early 2000s, a medium-term cluster during 2008–2012, and renewed fluctuations after 2015 linked to policy and capital flow shocks. Overall, the WPS highlights that both medium-term cycles ($\approx 1\text{--}2$ years) and short-term episodic shocks ($\approx 3\text{--}6$ months) dominate these variables, with significant clusters consistently overlapping with global crises.

Wavelet Transform Coherence (WTC) Analysis

The Wavelet Coherence (WTC) analysis provides a two-dimensional framework for examining the dynamic correlation between variables across both time and frequency domains, thereby allowing for the identification of time-varying co-movement patterns (Torrence & Compo, 1998; Rua, 2010). Figures derived from the analysis reveal the evolving relationship between global supply chain pressures (GSCPI) and three key macroeconomic drivers: oil prices (OIL), industrial production (IP), and the nominal effective exchange rate (EER) for OECD economies over the period 1998M1–2025M6. The color scale represents the strength of the coherence (blue = weak, red = strong), while the thick black contours indicate areas statistically significant at the 5% level. Phase arrows provide information on the direction of the lead-lag relationship.

GSCPI–OIL

The relationship between global supply chain pressures and oil prices shows pronounced coherence during major global shocks. Notably, periods around the 2008 global financial crisis, the 2014 oil price collapse, and the 2020 COVID-19 pandemic exhibit significant high-coherence zones at 0.5–2 year periodicities. These episodes are characterized by oil price volatility feeding into cost-push inflationary pressures and logistical disruptions, thereby intensifying supply chain stress (Baumeister & Kilian, 2016; Kilian, 2009).

Graph 6. Wavelet Coherence: GSCPI vs OIL

(Note: Red areas indicate high correlation, and arrows indicate the direction of the relationship. Right arrows indicate positive coordination, and upward arrows indicate the leading role of oil prices.)

Phase arrows in these high-coherence regions predominantly point rightward and slightly upward, indicating that oil prices tend to lead GSCPI, consistent with the view that energy price shocks transmit to broader economic supply networks through higher input costs and transport expenses (Elder & Serletis, 2010). However, occasional bidirectional arrows suggest that in some periods, elevated supply chain pressures may also exert feedback effects on commodity markets through demand-side constraints and stockpiling behavior (Baffes et al., 2015).

GSCPI–IP

The coherence between GSCPI and industrial production is particularly strong during the aftermath of the 2001 dot-com crisis, the 2008 financial crisis, and the COVID-19 pandemic, with significant zones at 1–4 year scales. These results indicate that demand-side shocks, as captured by changes in industrial activity, exert a substantial influence on supply chain stress during economic downturns (Carvalho et al., 2021).

Graph 7. Wavelet Coherence: GSCPI vs IP

(Note: Red areas indicate high correlation, and arrows indicate the direction of the relationship. Right arrows indicate positive coordination, and upward arrows indicate the leading role of industrial production.)

The phase dynamics reveal that, in most high-coherence zones, arrows point rightward, suggesting synchronous movement between industrial production and supply chain pressures. This synchronicity is consistent with the global manufacturing cycle literature, which links reductions in industrial output to logistical bottlenecks and upstream disruptions. In some shorter cycles, arrows point upward, implying that industrial production contractions lead increases in GSCPI, which aligns with demand shock transmission mechanisms (Peng and Wu, 2024; Ren et al., 2024; Klug, 2017; Klug, 2023).

GSCPI–EER

The link between GSCPI and the nominal effective exchange rate becomes more pronounced after 2010, with statistically significant coherence concentrated at 0.5–1 year frequencies. Exchange rate movements can impact supply chain stress through import price channels, especially in economies heavily reliant on foreign intermediate goods (Amiti et al., 2014; Gopinath, 2015). A depreciation in the domestic currency raises the local currency cost of imported inputs, thereby intensifying supply chain pressures.

Graph 8. Wavelet Coherence: GSCPI vs EER

(Note: Red areas indicate high correlation, and arrows indicate the direction of the relationship. Right arrows indicate positive coordination, and upward arrows indicate the leading role of effective exchange rates.)

Phase arrows exhibit mixed directions: in several instances, the EER leads GSCPI, consistent with exchange rate pass-through effects; in others, GSCPI appears to lead EER, potentially reflecting feedback loops where supply chain disruptions influence currency valuations via trade balance adjustments (Forbes et al., 2018).

The WTC findings underscore that the interplay between supply chain pressures and macroeconomic variables is state-dependent and frequency-specific. Crisis periods exhibit stronger coherence, particularly at medium-term periodicities, suggesting that both supply and demand shocks amplify during global downturns (Laumer and Schaffer, 2025; Mrabet et al., 2025; Finck and Tillmann, 2023).

From a policy perspective, these results imply that monetary and trade policymakers should adopt a time-frequency-aware approach to monitoring macroeconomic stability. For instance, oil price volatility and exchange rate depreciation should be closely tracked as potential leading indicators of rising supply chain stress, while industrial production downturns may signal demand-side amplification of supply bottlenecks. Integrating such insights into early warning systems could enhance the resilience of global trade and production networks.

CONCLUSION

The paper analyzes the factors behind the global supply chain pressures in OECD economies, paying attention to the asymmetric effects of oil prices, aggregate demand, and exchange rates. The article offers insight into the time-frequency dynamics characterizing global supply chain disruptions using wavelet power spectrum (WPS) and wavelet transform coherence (WTC) analysis from 1998 to 2025. Results also indicate that supply chain pressures are influenced by temporary shocks and structural cyclical forces that combine with worldwide macroeconomic factors, although it should be acknowledged that the dataset is limited to OECD economies and aggregate-level indicators, which may restrict the generalizability of the findings to other regions or to firm- and sector-level dynamics.

The analysis elicits three salient empirical insights. The first point is that oil prices have an overwhelming effect on stress in the supply chain, especially during times of elevated market volatility and geopolitical risk. Medium-term (1–2 year) cycles appear as the main channel for energy market shocks to have persistent effects on transportation and production costs. Second, industrial output reflects the demand-side aspect of supply chain constraints. Positive demand shocks exacerbate congestion effects, especially when global economic recoveries are concurrent, whereas production downturns are associated with less pressure, though asymmetrically so. Third, the impact of exchange rate movements on supply chain stress works mainly through the import cost channel due to direct pass-through effects and feedback around supply chain shocks to currency values in short to medium-run cycles. Nonetheless, because the wavelet methodology captures correlations in time–frequency space without establishing strict causality, the interpretation of lead–lag relationships should be treated with caution.

Collectively, these findings highlight that the global supply chain pressures are multi-dimensional by nature, influenced concurrently by cost-push (oil) and demand-pull (industrial production) forces, as well as the financial linkages (exchange rates). Most importantly, the findings underscore that structural shocks—such as the 2008 global financial crisis, the 2014 oil price crash, and the COVID-19 pandemic—strengthen the coherence of dynamics between supply chain stresses and macroeconomic substance, and thus imply that production networks are stressed more when the shocks are systemic.

These findings also bear important policy implications. Policymakers should understand that monitoring global oil market volatility and exchange rate movements is an early warning for supplier stress. What is more, demand spikes necessitate proactive efforts to build more logistics capacity, because bottlenecks accrue faster than they recede. As adopted in this research, the time–frequency approach to monitoring may thus provide a powerful set of methods for implementing

adaptive trade, monetary, and industry policies capable of increasing resilience against global shocks.

This paper adds to the existing literature on global supply chain dynamics by delivering an integrated cross-country investigation of OECD countries encompassing asymmetric, time-varying, and frequency-specific links. The results underscore the importance of including supply chain indicators like the GSCPI in macroeconomic analysis and policy formulation. Future work might also refine these analytics, for instance, into firm-level heterogeneity in supply chain exposure, or the interaction of global supply chain stress with shocks to the climate, thereby overcoming the current temporal and regional limitations and advancing our knowledge of how systemic vulnerabilities cascade through the global economy.

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